

Thermodynamic studies of ternary eutectic mixture $\text{KNO}_3 + \text{NaNO}_2 + \text{NaNO}_3$ at different temperatures

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Abstract : The internal pressure, energy of vaporization and heat of vaporization of pure components of ternary eutectic mixture $\text{KNO}_3 + \text{NaNO}_2 + \text{NaNO}_3$ were computed from the reported values of thermal expansivity and isothermal compressibility at different temperatures. These thermodynamic properties were also obtained for the eutectic mixture at two different compositions as a function of temperature.

Keywords : Eutectic mixture, thermodynamic study.

Introduction

The molten eutectic mixture $\text{KNO}_3 + \text{NaNO}_2 + \text{NaNO}_3$ has several advantages due to its exceptional heat transfer characteristics and low-cost operation at atmospheric pressure. Its thermal stability and a wide liquid temperature range provide with a good thermal heat storage operations. This mixture is non-corrosive and nontoxic. Due to the characteristic of $\text{KNO}_3 + \text{NaNO}_2 + \text{NaNO}_3$ molten mixture, Ganue¹ measured the viscosity and density of two different sets of mixtures over a wide range of temperatures. 53/40/7 wt% and 52/33.6/14.4 wt% mixtures of $\text{KNO}_3 + \text{NaNO}_2 + \text{NaNO}_3$ were undertaken for the determination of viscosity in the temperature range of 373–482 °C and 254–480 °C respectively. The functional relationship between viscosity and temperature was studied for both types of eutectic mixtures.

Formulation :

The internal pressure of each component of the ternary eutectic mixture is obtained from the relation

$$P_{\text{int},i} = \frac{\alpha_i T}{\beta_{T,i}} - P = \frac{\alpha_i T}{\beta_{T,i}} \quad (\text{when } P \text{ is low}) \quad (1)$$

where α_i and $\beta_{T,i}$ are respectively the thermal expansivity and isothermal compressibility of i -th component in the mixture ($\text{KNO}_3 + \text{NaNO}_2 + \text{NaNO}_3$). For calculating the internal pressure of eutectic mixture, $(P_{\text{int}})_{\text{eut,mix}}$, the mole fraction additivity has been normally employed in literature², i.e.

$$(P_{\text{int}})_{\text{eut,mix}} = \sum_{i=1}^3 x_i P_{\text{int},i} \quad (2)$$

where x_i is the mole fraction of the i -th component in the

mixture. Very recently² it has been suggested that the internal pressure of a mixture is volume fraction additive. The argument is based on the basis of definition of α and β_T . Thus, in present case we have

$$\alpha_{\text{eut,mix}} = \sum \Phi_i \alpha_i \quad (3)$$

$$\beta_{T,\text{eut,mix}} = \sum \Phi_i \beta_T \quad (4)$$

where Φ_i is the volume fraction of the pure eutectic component ($\text{KNO}_3 + \text{NaNO}_2 + \text{NaNO}_3$). α_i and $\beta_{T,i}$ are respectively the values of thermal expansivity and isothermal compressibility of pure components. The volume fraction Φ_i , is given by

$$\Phi_i = \frac{x_i V_i}{\sum x_i V_i} \quad (5)$$

where V_i is the molar volume of i -th component. In this way the exact value of internal pressure of ternary eutectic mixture is obtained from the equation

$$(P_{\text{int}})_{\text{eut,mix}} = \frac{T \sum \Phi_i \alpha_i}{\sum \Phi_i \beta_{T,i}} \quad (6)$$

Internal pressure gives a rough estimate of the energy of vaporization and heat of vaporization. For pure component of the eutectic mixture

$$\Delta E_i = (P_{\text{int}})_i V_i \quad (7)$$

$$\Delta H_i = \Delta E_i + RT \quad (8)$$

where ΔE_i and ΔH_i are respectively the energy of vaporization and heat of vaporization of pure components. For the ternary eutectic mixture, values are obtained from the relations

$$\Delta E_{\text{eut,mix}} = (P_{\text{int}})_{\text{eut,mix}} V_{\text{eut,mix}} \quad (9)$$

$$\Delta H_{\text{eut,mix}} = \Delta E_{\text{eut,mix}} + RT \quad (10)$$

where all the symbols have their usual notations.

Results and discussion

Gaune¹ viscosity data of the ternary eutectic mixture (KNO₃ + NaNO₂ + NaNO₃) have been analysed recently^{3,4} in the light of empirical equation and Flory statistical theory. The values of density, thermal expansivity and isothermal compressibility of pure eutectic components KNO₃, NaNO₂ and NaNO₃ are reported at different temperatures for two sets of compositions, $x_1 = 0.4396$, $x_2 = 0.4158$ and $x_1 = 0.4421$, $x_2 = 0.4885$. From the density data, we calculated the molar volumes of pure components. These are reported in the second, third and fourth columns of Table 1. The values^{3,4} of thermal expansivity (α) and isothermal compressibility (β_T) of pure components at different temperatures are also recorded in the same table. Internal pressure values obtained from eq. (1) are given in table for all the three

components of eutectic mixtures KNO₃, NaNO₂ and NaNO₃. Energy and heat of vaporization for the pure components as a function of temperature are computed from eqs. (7) and (8) respectively. These values are presented in Table 1.

Two sets of data are generated for the internal pressure, energy of vaporization and heat of vaporization in the case of ternary melts having two different compositions. One set of values are obtained on the basis of mole fraction additivity. Thus the values of $(P_{\text{int}})_{\text{mix}}$, ΔE_{mix} and ΔH_{mix} are calculated using eqs. (2), (9) and (10) respectively. The second set of values of these thermodynamic properties of ternary eutectic mixtures are computed from eqs. (6), (9) and (10). In this case the $(P_{\text{int}})_{\text{mix}}$ values obtained from eq. (6) are used in eqs. (9) and (10). These are the values obtained by the volume fraction additivity recently suggested².

The results of Table 1 reveal that in both sets of mole fractions, internal pressure, energy and enthalpy of vaporization of pure component increase as the temperature is increased. Similarly the results of Table 2 reveal that

Table 1. Calculated values of internal pressure, energy and enthalpy of vaporization for pure component at varying temperatures

Temp. (K)	V_1 (c.c.mol ⁻¹)	V_2 (c.c.mol ⁻¹)	V_3 (c.c.mol ⁻¹)	$P_{(\text{int})1}$ (atm)	$P_{(\text{int})2}$ (atm)	$P_{(\text{int})3}$ (atm)	ΔE_1 (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔE_2 (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔE_3 (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔH_1 (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔH_2 (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔH_3 (kJ mol ⁻¹)
Set-I ($x_1 = 0.4396$, $x_2 = 0.4158$)												
489	51.57	37.07	43.14	17439	17514	19738	91.13	65.79	86.27	95.19	69.85	90.34
599	53.77	38.78	44.93	20126	21076	24302	109.65	82.82	110.64	114.63	87.80	115.62
622	54.25	39.16	45.33	20723	21875	18304	113.92	86.80	84.06	119.09	91.97	89.23
655	54.97	39.71	45.90	21550	22898	26690	120.02	92.14	124.14	125.46	97.59	129.59
716	56.33	40.78	47.01	23308	24947	29117	133.03	103.09	138.70	138.99	109.04	144.65
753	57.19	41.46	47.71	23474	26160	30841	136.03	109.89	149.09	142.29	116.15	155.35
Set-II ($x_1 = 0.4421$, $x_2 = 0.4885$)												
457	50.96	36.60	42.64	16424	16679	18211	84.81	61.86	78.69	88.61	65.66	82.49
459	51.00	36.63	42.67	16510	16761	18120	85.32	62.21	78.35	89.13	66.03	82.17
481	51.42	36.94	43.01	17103	19083	18965	89.11	71.42	82.66	93.11	75.42	86.65
513	52.04	37.43	43.52	18111	18723	20287	95.49	71.01	89.45	99.75	75.28	93.72
575	53.28	38.40	44.53	19657	21047	22650	106.11	81.89	102.19	110.89	86.67	106.97
591	53.60	38.65	44.80	19971	21760	23214	108.47	85.22	105.37	113.38	90.14	110.29
646	54.77	39.56	45.75	21358	23589	25248	118.53	94.56	117.03	123.90	99.93	122.40
673	55.36	40.03	46.23	21935	24594	26428	123.04	99.74	123.78	128.64	105.34	129.38
698	55.92	40.46	46.68	22422	25514	27151	127.04	104.60	128.42	132.84	110.41	134.23
785	57.96	42.06	48.33	24005	28893	29774	140.97	123.14	145.81	147.50	129.67	152.33
789	58.05	42.14	48.41	24168	29090	30322	142.16	124.21	148.74	148.72	130.77	155.30
792	58.13	42.20	49.31	24110	28970	30477	142.00	123.87	152.28	148.59	130.45	158.87

Table 2. Calculated values of internal pressure, energy and enthalpy of vaporization for ternary eutectic mixture ($\text{KNO}_3 + \text{NaNO}_2 + \text{NaNO}_3$) at varying temperatures

Temp. (K)	$P_{\text{int(mix)}}$ eq. (2) (atm)	$P_{\text{int(mix)}}$ eq. (6) (atm)	$\Delta E_{\text{(mix)}}$ eq. (7) (kJ mol^{-1})	$\Delta E_{\text{(mix)}}$ eq. (9) (kJ mol^{-1})	$\Delta H_{\text{(mix)}}$ eq. (8) (kJ mol^{-1})	$\Delta H_{\text{(mix)}}$ eq. (10) (kJ mol^{-1})
Set-I ($x_1 = 0.4396, x_2 = 0.4158$)						
489	17803	17778	79.95	79.84	84.02	83.91
599	21124	20992	99.02	98.40	104	103.38
622	20852	20678	98.64	97.82	103.82	102.99
655	22854	22663	109.56	108.65	115.01	114.1
716	24829	24585	122.06	120.86	128.02	126.81
753	25656	25268	128.10	126.16	134.36	132.42
Set-II ($x_1 = 0.4421, x_2 = 0.4885$)						
457	16673	16647	73.27	73.16	77.07	76.96
459	16744	16721	73.64	73.53	77.45	77.35
481	18200	17988	80.70	79.76	84.7	83.76
513	18561	18502	83.33	83.07	87.6	87.33
575	20544	20402	94.51	93.85	99.29	98.63
591	21070	20881	97.54	96.67	102.46	101.6
646	22718	22475	107.53	106.38	112.9	111.75
673	23546	23246	112.69	111.26	118.29	116.85
698	24261	23903	117.32	115.60	123.13	121.4
785	26793	26172	134.45	131.33	140.98	137.86
789	26999	26374	135.72	132.58	142.28	139.14
792	26926	26312	135.69	132.59	142.27	139.18

the internal pressure calculated by eqs. (2) and (6), energy and enthalpy of vaporization calculated by eqs. (7),

(9) and eqs. (8), (10) respectively of ternary eutectic mixture also increase with the rise of temperature.

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